

Large-scale validation of forest attribute maps across different spatial resolutions

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Abstract

Fine-scale, spatially explicit forest attribute maps are essential for guiding forest management and policy decisions. Such maps, based on the combination of National Forest Inventory (NFI) and remote sensing datasets, have a long tradition in the Nordic countries. Harmonizing the pixel size among national forest attribute maps would considerably improve the utility of the maps for users. However, national forest attribute maps are often aligned with the NFI plot size, and the influence of creating these maps at different spatial resolutions is little studied. We assess the stand-level uncertainty of biomass, volume, basal area, and Lorey's height estimates resulting from the aggregation of maps across varying spatial resolutions. Models fit at 16 m native resolution were applied for predictions at pixels sizes (side lengths) of 1, 5, 10, 16, and 30 m. For validation, we use 65 independent stands that cover a total area of 24 ha. The stands are widely distributed over a large spatial and ecological extent in Norway. For all attributes, the lowest uncertainties, ranging from 6.86 % for Lorey's height to 13.86 % for volume, were observed for predictions at pixel sizes of 5 m to 16 m. The uncertainty changes across resolutions were generally small (< 5 %) for biomass, volume, and basal area. For Lorey's height, changing the spatial resolution resulted in large errors of up to 25 %. Overall, our findings suggest that the main forest attributes can be mapped at a finer scale without complex adjustments.

1. Introduction

Forests play a crucial role in the bioeconomy, for climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation (Dinerstein et al., 2019; Thompson, 2009; Griscom et al., 2017). Sustainable management practices require reliable information on forests' status and future development to minimize trade-offs and maximize synergies among the various ecosystem goods and services. Forest management at local scales is traditionally informed by Forest Management Inventories (FMIs). In the Nordic countries, FMIs are predominantly conducted using the Area-Based Approach (ABA) (Næsset, 2002; Hyypä et al., 2008; Maltamo et al., 2014) which combines Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS) and a limited number of field plots to provide fine-scale information about forest stands (Næsset et al., 2004; Maltamo et al., 2021). Over the last decade, the availability of national ALS campaigns has enabled the development of national forest attribute maps by utilizing in-situ data from National Forest Inventories (NFIs) (Nord-Larsen and Schumacher, 2012; Nilsson et al., 2017; Tuominen et al., 2017; Hauglin et al., 2021). This provides spatially explicit forest resource maps at a national scale (McRoberts et al., 2010; Kangas et al., 2018; Fassnacht et al., 2023). Consequently, the application of national forest attribute maps is increasingly considered in FMIs (Maltamo et al., 2021; Rahlf et al., 2021).

The sample plot size and spatial resolution of forest attribute maps are typically congruent in traditional FMIs (Næsset, 2014). This is to avoid systematic errors due to the use of resolution-dependent predictor and response variables in regression models (Magnussen et al., 2016). A metric is considered resolution independent if averaging over a certain number of adjacent cells (or pixels) yields the same results as if the metric were computed for the whole area as a single cell (Packalen et al., 2019). ALS

42 metrics such as mean height and proportion of echoes, meet the condition of resolution-
43 independence. However, other metrics like height quantiles and the number of echoes above specific
44 thresholds do not possess this property. Furthermore, response variables such as measures of mean
45 and total quantity per areal unit, are additive and therefore resolution independent (Köhl et al., 2006).
46 Examples of these include above-ground biomass, volume, and basal area. However, dominant and
47 mean height, which are not additive, are sensitive to spatial resolution (Magnussen et al., 2016;
48 Packalen et al., 2019). In real-world applications, a combination of resolution independent and
49 dependent predictor and response variables are typically utilized in forest attribute mapping (Næsset,
50 2002; Næsset et al., 2004).

51 The pixel size of national forest attribute maps often deviates, to a smaller or larger degree, from the
52 size of the NFI field plots (Kangas et al., 2018). This discrepancy can be attributed primarily to two
53 factors. Firstly, forest attributes in NFIs are frequently assessed on sample plots of varying sizes. For
54 example, many NFIs use concentric sample plots, where smaller trees are assessed on smaller circles
55 than larger trees (Tomppo et al., 2008). Secondly, for large-scale applications, practical considerations
56 related to data management and downstream analysis often influence the spatial resolution (Nilsson
57 et al., 2017). For instance, circular plots with a size of 250 m² as in the Norwegian NFI (Breidenbach et
58 al., 2020), would require pixels with a side length of ~15.8114 m. A map with such a pixel size would
59 be impractical on national scales as there will be no overlap with other existing mapping infrastructure.

60 While the analysis of resolution dependence in ABA is important, it remains a relatively underexplored
61 field of study. Packalen et al., (2019) systematically identified factors and quantified effects on
62 uncertainties with changing spatial resolutions when applying the ABA. Their study was conducted on
63 a pine-dominated study-site in Finland where the biomass of all trees on 58 plots with a size of 25 m ×
64 25 m was measured. This setup enabled various combinations of fitting and prediction at spatial
65 resolutions across 8.33, 12.5, and 25 m pixel sizes. They found that if models with resolution-
66 independent variables were used to predict at a finer resolution than the fitted (native) resolution, it
67 resulted in a decrease of random errors, and in tendency a systematic underestimation. If the models
68 were applied at a coarser prediction resolution than the fitted resolution, it resulted in increased
69 random error, and in tendency a systematic overestimation. They concluded that the resolution effect
70 is minimal in the case of up to 4-times changes of the resolution. This suggests that in practical
71 scenarios, a mismatch in spatial resolution between model fitting and applied prediction can be
72 acceptable for forest attribute mapping. However, this study was conducted on a local site in Finland
73 and focused solely on biomass. Nilsson et al. (2017) analyzed in Sweden the changes in random error
74 for volume and Lorey's height forest attributes across 10 m to 20 m resolutions. They found that,
75 despite the native resolution of the Swedish forest resource map being 25 m based on the NFI plot size,
76 the predicted maps with a resolution of 12.5 m were found to be satisfactory for producing the national
77 forest attribute maps.

78 Our aim is to assess the prediction accuracy, in terms of random and systematic errors, of the models
79 used in the Norwegian forest attribute map (Astrup et al., 2019; Hauglin et al., 2021) when applied
80 across varying spatial resolutions. More specifically, we analyze the changes in prediction accuracy of
81 models that were fitted at 16 m native resolution when applied to predict forest attributes for pixels
82 with side lengths between 1 and 30 m. We aggregate the pixel-level predictions to stand-level estimates
83 and analyze the resulting uncertainty for the forest attributes biomass, volume, basal area, and Lorey's
84 height. Independent field measurements of 65 stands widely distributed across Norway are used as a
85 reference.

86 2. Materials and Methods

87 2.1. Overview and study area

88 The Norwegian forest attribute map is a collection of spatially explicit raster layers with a pixel size of
89 16 m x 16 m which includes predicted forest attributes of biomass, volume, basal area, and Lorey's
90 height (Hauglin et al., 2021). The raster layers are generated from univariate linear mixed-effect models
91 that utilize NFI data, country-wide ALS, and additional auxiliary data products. The map covers all
92 forested areas in Norway, approximately 12 Mha, and is openly available at Kilden (NIBIO, 2024).

93 Forests cover ~38% of Norway's total land area and are predominantly situated in the boreal climate
94 zone. The forests are dominated by three main tree species: Norway spruce, Scots pine, and deciduous
95 trees, primarily birch, which are often mixed with the coniferous species. The country has a diverse
96 topographical variation including both lowland and mountainous areas.

97 The independent field validation data used in this study are located across the whole of the country,
98 including the South-Eastern, Central-Southern, Western, and Northern geographic regions (Figure 1).
99 Overall, 65 stands have been used with sizes ranging from 0.1 to 1.7 ha and an average of 0.4 ha.
100 Altogether, the stands cover covers 24 hectares.

101 Further details on the models used in producing Norwegian forest attribute maps, the independent
102 field data, and the study design are given in sections 2.2, 2.3, and 2.4.

103 2.2. The Norwegian Forest Attribute Map

104 2.2.1. National Forest Inventory data

105 The NFI is a continuously operating inventory based on a permanent sample grid where 1/5 of the plots
106 are measured annually (Breidenbach et al., 2020). The sample grid size in productive forest is 3 km x
107 3 km. The NFI field measurements are carried out within circular 250 m² plots. Diameter at breast
108 height (dbh) and species of all trees with a dbh \geq 5 cm are recorded. The tree height of 10 trees are
109 measured. Using these measurements together with species-specific models, missing tree heights,
110 timber volume (with bark), and aboveground biomass are predicted for the trees at the sample plots.
111 Tree-level measurements are scaled-up to plot-level values including Lorey's height and basal area.
112 More detailed information on the Norwegian NFI can be found in Breidenbach et al., (2020). The
113 complied training data consists of 14196 NFI plots from the inventory cycle 2018-2022.

114 2.2.2. Predictor variables

115 The predictor variables for estimating forest attributes are derived from country-wide ALS data. The
116 country-wide ALS data have been acquired by national flight campaigns organized by the Norwegian
117 Mapping Agency which covers most of the country, except high mountainous areas (Hauglin et al,
118 2021). In this study the following predictor variables have been used: mean height of first returns
119 (hmean_first), the square of the mean height of first returns (hmean_first_sq), proportion of first
120 returns above 2m (prop_ab2m_first) and 95th height percentile of first returns (h95_first). Additionally,
121 the topographical slope (slope) has been calculated based on the 1 m x 1 m resolution digital terrain
122 model. A further explanatory variable was the time difference between the ALS acquisition date and
123 field date expressed as a decimal number of growth seasons (time_diff).

124 2.2.3. Regression models

125 The Norwegian forest attribute maps are generated as wall-to-wall predictions of univariate linear
126 mixed-effects regression models (Pinheiro and Bates, 2006). These models accommodate systematic
127 differences between ALS projects (described in 2.2.1.) and regions by incorporating random effects.
128 The regions are natural geographic divisions within Norway (Figure 1). The predictor variables used in

129 the models were selected through a stepwise process using leave-one-out cross-validation and expert
 130 knowledge, as described in Hauglin et al., 2021. In this study, we used the models to predict above-
 131 ground biomass, volume, basal area, and Lorey's height. The models were fitted separately for each
 132 dominant tree species group (spruce, pine, and deciduous forests). The general model form of the
 133 models is

$$y_{ijk} = \beta_0 + (b_i + b_{1ij} + \beta_1) \times x_{1ijk} + \beta_2 \times x_{2ijk} \dots + \beta_k \times x_{pijk} + \varepsilon_{ijk}$$

$$i=1,\dots,r, j=1,\dots,m_i, k=1, \dots, n_{ij}, b_i \sim N(0, \sigma_b^2), b_{1ij} \sim N(0, \sigma_{b1}^2), \varepsilon_{ijk} \sim N(0, \sigma_\varepsilon^2) \quad (1)$$

134 where y_{ijk} is the forest attribute at plot k within ALS project j and region i; r is the number of regions;
 135 p is the number of explanatory variables x ; β are the fixed effects regression parameters and b_i
 136 indicates a predicted random effect. Random slope parameters b for region i and b1 for ALS project
 137 area ij are defined as the most influential explanatory variable x_1 . The terms n_{ij} and m_i represent the
 138 number of field plots within an ALS project and the total number of ALS projects respectively. The
 139 variance of the random effect is denoted by σ_b^2 , and σ_ε^2 refers to the residual variance. Four types of
 140 combinations of explanatory variables (introduced in section 2.2.2) have been used for predicting the
 141 species-specific forest attributes:

- 142 i) hmean_first (x_1) + hmean_first_sq + time_diff + slope + prop_ab2m_first
 143 for predicting biomass, volume and basal area for spruce and broadleaf
- 144 ii) hmean_first (x_1) + hmean_first_sq + time_diff + prop_ab2m_first
 145 for predicting basal area for pine
- 146 iii) hmean_first (x_1) + hmean_first_sq + time_diff + slope
 147 for predicting volume for pine
- 148 iv) h95_first (x_1) + time_diff + slope + prop_ab2m_first
 149 for predicting Lorey's height for spruce, pine and broadleaf

150 The predictor variables are resolution-independent in the case of hmean_first, hmean_first_sq, and
 151 prop_ab2m_first assuming the number of echoes per cell is constant. The variable h95_first is a
 152 resolution-dependent predictor variable since height percentiles are not unbiased corresponding to
 153 the population parameters (Magnussen et al., 2016; Packalen et al., 2019). Additionally, the slope is
 154 also a resolution-independent predictor variable.

155 2.3. Validation stands

156 We utilized stand-level observations, measured independently from the NFI field observations, as
 157 validation datasets. Two sets of stand-level datasets were available for this study. The first dataset
 158 resulted from field campaigns conducted in two geographic regions in Norway: Asker municipality in
 159 the eastern region and Alver municipality in the western region (Figure 1). In Asker, assessments were
 160 carried out across 21 forest stands during September and October 2020, while in Alver, 18 forest stands
 161 were measured during July and August 2020. Within each forest stand, 10-15 plots of 250 m² were
 162 measured, following the standard NFI plot measurement protocol (as described in Section 2.2.1.). The
 163 39 stands covered a total area of 11 ha.

164 The second dataset consists of long-term field trials established to assess different silvicultural
 165 approaches, and forest management methods to evaluate forest growth. We used the field trials
 166 measured after 2018 where precise coordinates were available. This included measurements from
 167 2018, 2020, 2021, and 2022. The selected field trials consist of 1-30 rectangular plots located spatially
 168 close to each other (Figure 1) where the plot areas range from 0.02 to 0.30 ha (average area 0.06 ha).
 169 The dbh and tree species of each tree within the plots are recorded, while the height for every fourth
 170 tree is measured. The height of the remaining trees is predicted based on the measured tree heights.

171 Species-specific allometric equations are applied to predict the tree-level biomass and volume. The
172 tree-level information is then used to calculate plot-level information of biomass, volume, basal area,
173 and Lorey's height. We used 26 field trials located in the East, Central-South and North regions of
174 Norway that covered a total area of 13 ha. A summary of the stand-level validation dataset can be
175 found in Table 1.

176 2.4. Study design

177 Our study encompassed four main steps (Figure 2) including a) fitting of regression models at 16 m
178 resolution using NFI plots b) processing of the ALS data for the independent field validation stands
179 including the extraction of predictor variables at various spatial resolutions, c) prediction of forest
180 attributes at different spatial scales using the models trained at a 16 m resolution, d) analysis of the
181 prediction accuracy at varying spatial scales.

182 In step a), models for each measurement year of the validation data (2018, 2020, 2021, and 2022) were
183 fitted (Figure 2a) to match the validation field measurement date. This has been achieved by forecasting
184 and backcasting the observed increments at the NFI plots for the field observation date. In this way,
185 inconsistency between the prediction date and the validation field measurement date was avoided.
186 The predictor variables and regression models are described in sections 2.2.2 and 2.2.3.

187 In step b), we processed the ALS data at 1, 5, 10, 16, and 30 m spatial resolutions (Figure 2b) for the
188 validation stands (Figure 1). We selected the ALS projects that were acquired closest in time to the field
189 measurement date. The predictor variables were calculated for modeling biomass, volume, basal area,
190 and Lorey's height (the specific metrics are described in Section 2.2.2.). We calculated the time
191 difference between the ALS acquisition date and the validation field measurement date, expressed as
192 the number of growing seasons. Additionally, we resampled the dominant tree species (Breidenbach
193 et al., 2021) and slope rasters from 16 m x 16 m resolution to the tested resolutions using nearest
194 neighbor and bilinear interpolation. Information related to the ALS project and the geographic region
195 was also added for the modeling process.

196 In step c), we applied the regression models to predict biomass, volume, basal area, and Lorey's height
197 at the different spatial resolutions for the pixels covering the validation stands (Figure 2c). We then
198 estimated forest attributes for the validation stands by calculating the mean of the predicted forest
199 attributes at stand-level (Figure 2d). Pixel predictions were weighted according to the proportion by
200 which they covered the plots to account for the fact that not all pixels fully fall within them. The
201 observed and predicted values on plot-level were then averaged on stand level. This process resulted
202 in a dataset with (synthetic) estimates of forest attributes based on different pixel sizes which was used
203 in the accuracy assessment.

204 In step d), the accuracy was evaluated by calculating the weighted root mean squared error (RMSE)
205 and the weighted mean deviance (MD), taking into consideration the varying area sizes of the validation
206 stands by

$$\{RMSE, MD\} = \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^\varphi \right]^\omega \quad (3)$$

207 with $\varphi = 2$ and $\omega = 0.5$ for RMSE and $\varphi = 1$ and $\omega = 1$ for MD, where y_i and \hat{y}_i represent the observed and
208 estimated forest attributes, and w_i is the area of each validation stand; $i = 1, \dots, n$ with $n = 65$ indexes the
209 validation stands. The relative RMSE and MD were calculated by dividing RMSE and MD by the mean
210 of the observed values and multiplying the result by 100.

211 3. Results

212 In the stand-level validation of the Norwegian forest attribute map at its native resolution (16 m), the
213 RMSEs were found to be 15.21%, 13.93%, 11.97%, and 6.87% for biomass, volume, basal area, and
214 Lorey's height, respectively (Table 2). The MD indicated an underestimation of $\leq 4.42\%$ for biomass,
215 volume and, Lorey's height, and a slight overestimation for basal area (-0.10%) (Figure 3, Table 2).
216 Especially spruce-dominated stands with high biomass and volume tended to be underestimated
217 (Figure 3a,b).

218 The uncertainty (RMSE) for basal area changed the least when changing the resolution and the highest
219 accuracy was observed at the native resolution. For the other attributes, the highest accuracy was not
220 observed at the native resolution (16 m) but at 5 m (biomass and volume) and 10 m (Lorey's height)
221 resolution (Table 2). The uncertainty across 1-30 m spatial resolutions (Table 2) showed a similar
222 pattern for all attributes as it was highest for 1 m and 30 m, and increased towards the pixel size with
223 the highest accuracy (Figure 4a-d). The RMSEs ranged from 13.86 % to 19.53 % for biomass, 12.64 % to
224 18.58 % for volume. For Lorey's height, the uncertainty decreased with increasing spatial resolutions
225 from 1 m to the native resolution (16 m) and increased at 30 m resolution (Figure 4e-h). Overall, the
226 RMSE changes are relatively small (<5.95) for the three additive attributes. For Lorey's height as a non-
227 additive attribute, the changes in uncertainty were higher (18.41 %).

228 The changes in systematic error across varying spatial resolutions showed a similar pattern as the total
229 uncertainty. Overall, the smallest systematic error was observed at a 5 m resolution for biomass,
230 volume, and at the native resolution for basal area. As an exception, the lowest systematic error for
231 Lorey's height was at 30 m resolution. The systematic errors of biomass, volume, and basal area
232 decreased from 1 m to 5 m, followed by an increasing trend up to 30 m resolution (Table 2, Figure 4a-
233 d). In contrast, the systematic errors of Lorey's height decreased from 1 m to 30 m (Table 2, Figure g-
234 h). While the differences in systematic errors for biomass, volume, and basal area were relatively small
235 ($< 5.37\%$), Lorey's height had larger changes (22.51 %).

236 We observe similar trends across spatial resolutions when comparing random and systematic errors of
237 dominant species to the results for all species (Table 2). For spruce stands, RMSE values range from
238 6.88% to 25.97% and MD values range from -1.79% to 24.87%, which aligned with the aggregated
239 results. For pine stands, the RMSE values ranged from 6.59% to 25.72% and MD values ranged from -
240 1.99% to 24.8% across all forest attributes, comparable with the aggregated results. However, the
241 lowest uncertainties for volume are observed at 5 m resolution. Because broadleaf stands consist of
242 only four observations, they are included in Table 2 solely for completeness.

243 4. Discussion

244 We evaluated the uncertainty of forest attribute maps (biomass, volume, basal area, and Lorey's height)
245 fitted at a nominal resolution of 16 m and used them to predict spatial resolutions ranging from 1 to
246 30 m. Except for Lorey's height, the models use resolution-independent explanatory variables. The
247 resulting estimates on stand level were compared to independent reference data.

248 The independent validation of the Norwegian forest attribute map at its native resolution showed
249 lower uncertainties compared to previous studies. The RMSE values reported in this study are smaller
250 by 5 to 21 % compared to those of the cross-validation result of the Norwegian forest attribute map
251 (Hauglin et al., 2021) and an independent validation conducted with forest management inventories
252 (de Lera Garrido et al., 2023). The MD values are in line with those reported by de Lera Garrido et al.,
253 2023 (MD ranging from 2 to 5 %), where independent field validation has been used. However, different
254 approaches have been used to evaluate the accuracy of the predicted forest attributes. Hauglin et al.,

255 2021 assessed the accuracies at the plot level where the uncertainties are larger, and de Lera Garrido
256 evaluated the accuracies by back casting the forest attributes maps to agree with the FMI field
257 observation dates. The overall accuracies of volume, basal area, and Lorey's height in our study are
258 comparable with those reported in the Swedish forest attribute map by Nilsson et al., 2017.

259 The estimation of biomass, volume, and Lorey's height in our study showed that the lowest random
260 errors (RMSE) were not achieved at the native resolution, but at a 5 or 10 m resolution. As suggested
261 by Packalen et al. (2019), this may be attributed to the fact that metrics derived from larger plots tend
262 to yield regression coefficients that more accurately represent the true values at a finer spatial scale.
263 For basal area, we found that the highest accuracy was achieved at the native resolution, however, the
264 difference in RMSE at 5 and 10 m resolution was less than 1 %. Our findings regarding the trends in
265 changes in RMSE at different spatial resolutions are in agreement with those from Packalen et al., 2019,
266 who reported a slight decrease in RMSE for both resolution dependent and independent linear models
267 for biomass at a finer spatial scale (-0.05% to -0.34%) and a slight increase in RMSE at a coarser spatial
268 resolution (0 to 0.15%). We found this trend also applicable for volume, while it was only partly
269 applicable for basal area and Lorey's height. These two forest attributes show increased RMSE at 5 and
270 1 m resolutions. Nilsson et al., (2017) reported a small decrease in RMSE in the case of predicting
271 volume and Lorey's height at finer resolution in northern Sweden (changes in RMSE are 0.4 % and 0.1
272 %, respectively), which is in agreement with our findings. They, however, also reported a slight increase
273 in RMSE for volume in Southern Sweden (2.1 %) and for Lorey's height (0.1 %). We also examined the
274 RMSE trends with changing spatial resolutions according to the dominant species. The results suggest
275 that comparable RMSE values achieved across all forest attributes and trends as observed in the
276 aggregated results (Table 2).

277 We observe a slight underestimation for all attributes at the native resolution which is likely due to the
278 fact that we used completely independent field validation data following slightly different
279 measurement approaches and dates compared to the modelling data. Nonetheless, for the models
280 with scale-independent variables (biomass, volume, and basal area) for spatial resolutions of 5-30m,
281 we see the same trend as reported by Packalen et al. (2019) for biomass. The systematic error
282 decreases when decreasing the pixel size relative to the native resolution and increases when
283 increasing the pixel size relative to the native resolution. However, we also observed an increasing trend
284 of the systematic error again at the finest resolution of 1 m. The dominant species-specific changes in
285 systematic error across varying spatial resolutions overall showed the same trends compared to the
286 aggregated results, just starting at different levels for the native resolution. Overall, it is a well-known
287 issue that model-predicted maps based on remote sensing and empirical models result in biased
288 estimates when aggregated (Breidenbach et al., 2022; Ståhl et al., 2024). However, unbiasedness is not
289 a strict requirement at stand level as long as biases are not too large. It has also been shown that maps
290 with large systematic errors can be used to improve estimates if sufficient reference data are available
291 (Räty et al., 2023).

292 Our study found that changes in random and systematic errors for the additive forest attributes are
293 small, a finding that is consistent with the results of Packalen et al., (2019). They reported that
294 resolution-independent predictor variables in the case of additive forest attributes such as biomass, a
295 4-times difference in resolution will have a negligible effect on the accuracy. We have further found
296 that this result can be expanded for other additive forest attributes such as volume and basal area, and
297 even a 16-times difference in resolution does not substantially affect the accuracy. Also, our study
298 suggests that with certain limitations and cautions, even Lorey's height can be predicted at a different
299 resolution than the NFI plot size as long as the resolution difference is less than 2 times compared to
300 the native resolution. This finding aligns with Nilsson et al. (2017), which has already been operationally

301 used to fit models for Lorey's height at 25 m native resolution while predicting maps with 12.5 m
302 resolution.

303 5. Conclusion

304 Growing accessibility of spatially explicit, nationwide forest attribute maps showcases their potential
305 to provide wall-to-wall information about forest ecosystems, which can be used as a comprehensive
306 knowledge base for various forest monitoring tasks. The required spatial resolution of these
307 applications can deviate from the spatial resolution of map pixels given the reference plots. For
308 instance, the proposed regulation on the European Forest Monitoring System allows countries to
309 provide harmonized forest attribute maps at 10 m resolution, which typically will deviate the NFI plot
310 sizes across the countries. Our results reveal that in an operational setting, the forest attribute models
311 fitted at the NFI plot size can be used to predict finer spatial scales without large differences in random
312 or systematic errors. Without the application of complex statistical scaling methods, the fitted model
313 at the NFI plot size can be used to produce forest attribute maps at a 10 or 5 m spatial scale that even
314 resulted in slightly improved estimates on stand level. Even for extreme resolutions such as 1 m pixel
315 size, the area-based approach can result in acceptable uncertainties for additive forest attributes such
316 as biomass, volume, and basal area.

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322 Author contributions

323 ZK conducted all data analyses, managed the study, and wrote the first draft. JB conceived the study,
324 supervised the work, wrote parts of the manuscript, and acquired funding. Both authors accept the
325 final version of the manuscript.

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417 *Table 1 Summary statistics of field-based estimations of biomass, volume, basal area, and Lorey's height in the aggregated*
418 *stand-level datasets. The table includes the minimum (min), maximum (max), mean, and standard deviation (sd) for each*
419 *attribute. Additionally, statistics related to the area of the stands are provided. The total number of validation stands is 65*
420 *and the total covered area is 24 hectares.*

	Biomass [Mg ha⁻¹]	Volume [m³ha⁻¹]	Basal area [m²ha⁻¹]	Lorey's height [m]	Area [ha]
min	68.67	100.62	15.69	9.93	0.12
max	583.71	984.35	71.25	30.40	1.74
mean	211.85	359.68	37.49	18.88	0.37
sd	118.28	208.88	14.41	4.46	0.29

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423 *Table 2 Stand-level estimates for biomass, volume, basal area, and Lorey's height, given predictions at different spatial*
 424 *resolutions, are subject to random (RMSE) and systematic (MD) uncertainties. The results for deciduous stands are derived*
 425 *from a limited number of observations (n=4) and are provided solely for the sake of completeness.*

		All species, n=65							
		Biomass		Volume		Basal area		Lorey's height	
		RMSE [%]	MD [%]	RMSE [%]	MD [%]	RMSE [%]	MD [%]	RMSE [%]	MD [%]
Resolution	1	14.99	4.34	13.61	2.92	12.55	1.15	25.27	24.05
	5	13.86	2.89	12.64	1.61	12.08	-0.99	9.08	7.46
	10	14.17	3.63	12.96	2.46	11.99	-0.73	6.86	3.87
	16	15.21	4.42	13.93	3.41	11.97	-0.10	6.87	2.38
	30	19.53	7.79	18.58	6.98	13.20	2.52	7.38	1.54
Spruce, n=30									
Resolution	1	14.32	8.28	13.45	7.21	11.13	1.52	25.97	24.87
	5	12.31	5.87	11.92	4.97	10.19	-1.59	9.61	8.33
	10	12.78	6.08	12.54	5.36	10.09	-1.79	6.88	4.22
	16	13.81	6.61	13.47	6.01	9.98	-1.50	6.91	2.45
	30	19.67	10.32	19.76	10.16	12.18	1.52	7.20	1.62
Pine, n=31									
Resolution	1	12.88	-1.79	12.49	-1.99	13.39	0.77	25.72	24.8
	5	13.45	-1.82	12.27	-1.97	13.13	-0.35	8.61	7.18
	10	13.63	-0.25	12.40	-0.42	13.31	0.44	6.70	3.89
	16	14.42	0.99	13.12	0.97	12.99	1.39	6.59	2.68
	30	15.65	3.98	14.67	4.14	13.67	3.74	7.40	1.86
Broadleaf, n=4									
Resolution	1	18.01	4.39	13.16	-4.78	16.28	0.84	14.35	12.87
	5	18.74	3.53	14.71	-5.63	17.41	-0.47	7.31	3.18
	10	18.45	4.38	13.27	-4.93	16.31	-0.19	7.14	1.26
	16	19.88	5.1	15.08	-3.86	17.82	0.77	7.66	-0.23
	30	19.79	7.99	12.49	-2.74	16.13	2.09	8.01	-1.32

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Figure 1 Overview of the study area and the independent validation datasets. The left side is an overview map of Norway that shows the geographic regions (South-East, Central-South, West, Mid, and North) and the dominant tree species. Red polygons indicate the independent validation stands. The right side shows selected areas (A and B) in higher detail with orthophotos in the background. The maps are in the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) coordinate system zone 33. The dominant tree species map is from Kilden (NIBIO, 2024), and orthophotos from Georange (2024).

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Figure 2 Overview of the workflow used for assessing the prediction accuracy of Norwegian forest attribute models predicted at different spatial scales (1-30 m). The input datasets are indicated with rounded rectangles, the main steps (corresponding to a-d in the main text) are in grey rectangles, and intermediate data and processing steps are indicated with dashed rectangles respectively.

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Figure 3 Observed (field-based) versus estimated (lidar-based) values at the native resolution of the Norwegian forest attribute map at 16 m pixel size for each examined forest attribute (a: biomass, b: volume, c: basal area and d: Lorey's height). The color of the dots indicates the dominant tree species within the validation stands.

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447 *Figure 4 Right column: Observed (field-based) versus estimated (lidar-based) values across different spatial resolutions for*
 448 *each forest attribute (a: biomass, c: volume, e: basal area, g: Lorey's height). Left column: Corresponding boxplots illustrate*
 449 *the distribution of the difference between observed and estimated values at each spatial resolution and forest attributes (b:*
 450 *biomass, d: volume, f: basal area, h: Lorey's height). The red dots indicate the area-weighted mean value of the difference*
 451 *between observed and estimated values.*

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